

BIBLIOGRAPHIC AND NUMERIC DATA BASES FOR

FIBER COMPOSITES AND MATRIX MATERIALS*

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We have been conducting research leading to the creation of bibliographic and numeric data bases of material properties, under contract with DOE's Division of Energy Storage Systems (DOE/STOR). We have created both bibliographic and numeric data bases for fiber composites and matrix materials, with particular emphasis to their application to modern flywheel technology. The bibliographic data base was created to provide a direct means to visually examine pertinent literature. The numeric data base is being created to provide evaluated materials properties data for direct input to applications programs. These and related data bases are being prepared to serve DOE/STOR administrators and their contractors in the expanding field of energy storage. Data bases and their evaluation programs will be stored on a PDP-11/70 computer system at LLL and be available for interactive use over the ARPAnet and by telephone dialup.

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SUMMARY

The Data Management Group at the Lawrence Livermore Laboratory is conducting research leading to the creation of data bases for energy storage systems. These data bases are computer-based and will contain bibliographic information, material properties data, and data on essential criteria for energy storage systems. Access to these central files will be from remote terminals over computer networks and by telephone dialup, in addition to the more conventional means of computer-generated reporting, and dissemination on magnetic tapes.

To validate the material properties data, a working agreement has been established between the Lawrence Livermore Laboratory (LLL) and the National Bureau of Standards (NBS). The Office of Standard Reference Data at NBS coordinates and monitors data evaluations by recognized national data evaluation centers. Two of the five data requests, for molten salts and for beta aluminas (battery materials) have been completed and the data is being entered into data bases for battery and thermal energy storage materials. Portions of two other data requests, for selected properties of metal alloys (flywheel materials) and metallic hydrides (hydrogen storage materials), have been received and are being prepared for computerization. Work on the remaining data request, for composite materials (flywheel materials), is currently in progress. A bibliographic data base for flywheel energy storage has been created and published. In addition, a comprehensive bibliography for molten salts and TES materials is in preparation.

1. Introduction and Background

"Research Leading to the Production and Early Use of Numeric Data Banks of Material Properties and System Analysis" has been carried out since February 1976, by the Data Management Group of LLL under contract to the U. S. Department of Energy and the Division of Energy Storage Systems (DOE/STOR), under contract number E(49-1)-3835. (1).

Many alternate energy storage systems are undergoing continued research and development: thermal, chemical, electrochemical, battery, physical, etc. The technological efficiency of these systems and their cost effectiveness often depend in large measure upon the properties of materials and substances in heretofore uncharted operational domains. Technical and economical feasibility is the central issue in the decision-making process. Basic data on material properties, and on characterizations of energy storage systems, are required to provide a reliable foundation for these activities.

Data bases of this type are being created as an essential part of this project. When completed, they will contain evaluated physical and chemical properties for materials used in energy storage systems and information and data to characterize the validity domains of the systems. The NBS and selected data evaluation centers are collaborating. These computerized data banks are being made available to industry and to universities. As such, they will serve as a public resource for the scientific and technological research community. It is anticipated that data bases of this type will provide a solid and expanding basis for the accelerating research activities in energy storage. They should help to eliminate discrepancies and should be a valuable aid to channel work into promising directions.

A staff of up to five professionals are participating in the project at LLL. Their academic backgrounds and experience are in chemistry,

metallurgy, and computer science. Project activity during the past year has centered around the publication of a bibliographic data base for flywheel energy storage (2), the computerization of evaluated molten salts data received from NBS, and acquisition of a PDP-11/70 computer system on which energy-storage-related data will reside. General energy storage data will be made available on the PDP-11/70 computer system over the ARPAnet, a national computer network, and by telephone dialup later in FY 1978.

2. Technological Data Base Activities

Our major technological data base activities include the identification and the evaluation of materials and their properties required for energy storage systems, and the creation of bibliographic and evaluated material properties data banks for user-oriented manipulation and dissemination. During the past year, we have acquired a computer system that is being prepared to handle these data banks for DOE's Division of Energy Storage.

2.1 Identification of Materials and Properties for Flywheel Energy Storage Systems

The identification of materials and properties for flywheels was carried out in collaboration with the flywheel research activities at LLL and with Sandia Laboratories. Based on an initial survey and on feedback obtained directly from users and researchers, requests for data on flywheel metals and composite materials have been sent to the NBS for evaluation (see Section 2.2).

2.2 Critical Evaluation of Material Properties

The critical evaluation of material properties is now in progress through a formal working agreement between LLL and NBS. Under this agreement, the NBS Office of Standard Reference Data, which manages the National Standard Reference Data System (NSRDS), acts as the mandated monitoring agency for the evaluation of material properties. The actual evaluations are carried out by nationally recognized evaluation centers affiliated with NSRDS/NBS. Computerization of the data and its transfer into the public domain is carried out by LLL. The data will also be published in a special series by NSRDS/NBS.

2.3 Bibliography on Fiber Composites and Flywheel Technology

A selected bibliography for fiber composites and flywheel energy storage has been published (2). It contains citations on the properties and mechanics of fibers, fiber composites, matrix materials, and on flywheel energy storage systems. The materials and flywheel systems citations were derived from the world literature. The bibliography is machine produced and is generated in two parts: A concordance on keywords and phrases, and the chronological listing of all bibliographic citations (Section 3.1). An updated bibliography is being published for the Second International Conference on Composite Materials.

2.4 Molten Salts/TES Bibliography

A comprehensive molten salts/TES bibliographic data base is being created in a similar way as the flywheel bibliography. Major sources of machine readable citations have been received from Dr. George Janz of the Molten Salts Data Center at the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute (approximately 4000 citations) and from Sandia Laboratories Fused Salt Bibliography (approximately 3000 citations). Sources of hardcopy citations include a

M.S. thesis by L. S. Charnoff (approximately 4000 citations) and other citations from ongoing literature searches at LLL. These bibliographic sources (3-6) are being combined into a single data bank which will be completed during FY 1978 for general use.

2.5 Molten Salts/TES Material Properties Data Base

A molten salts/TES material properties data base is under development for interactive use on our dedicated PDP-11/70 computer system. In addition to the inorganic salts data already computerized (7, 8), we have added the evaluated molten salts/TES material properties data received during the past year from Dr. George Janz. These data include values of up to 15 properties on 67 salt systems.

2.6 Computer System to Handle Storage Data

A PDP-11/70 computer system is being set up on the ARPAnet for storage, manipulation, and dissemination of energy-storage-related data. The basic computer system was procured and tested during the past year. In FY 1978, additional capability will be installed to enable both technological data bases, and other energy-storage related data bases, to be accessed directly over the ARPAnet or by telephone dialup.

3. Description of Flywheel-Related Data Bases

We are creating both bibliographic and evaluated materials properties data bases for flywheel-related applications as previously mentioned. An updated flywheel bibliography is being published for the Second International Conference on Composite Materials in Toronto. A numeric data base for flywheel materials is currently being developed in anticipation of the receipt of evaluated data from NBS.

3.1 Fiber Composites and Flywheel Bibliography

The fiber composites and flywheel bibliography consists of two sections: (1) A concordance that serves as a subject and author index, containing key words and phrases, authors, and organizations; and (2) the bibliographic listing of citations. This format is planned for future bibliographies and other subjects in the field of energy storage.

The entire bibliography owes its existence to computer technology. It is, in a sense, merely a printed copy of part of a computerized data base. As a printed copy it is static; the data base itself is not. Several advantageous aspects of computerization are reflected in this publication.

One aspect of computerization is the opportunity to quickly look up specific information, such as what authors may have published articles on a certain subject in a given time period. Such information can be retrieved in a fraction of the time it would take to do a literature search. It should be noted that other information exists in the data base, but is not pertinent for this bibliography.

A second aspect is the ease with which statistics can be generated; for example, the number of publications by author in a certain field or by center of research in a given subject.

A third aspect is the advantage of using a computer to create the recorded bibliography. Rapid updating is possible by merely adding new entries as they appear in the literature. In fact, whole blocks of records

from other data bases can be transferred by computer. Upgrading the concordance then creates a new edition ready for printing, a process much faster than conventional publishing methods. Thus, vast amounts of readily accessible data become available to the user quickly.

A final aspect is that professional value judgements play a very important role throughout the whole process. Specific terms are included or rejected, editing rules are defined, and a report structure is set up. In this manner human intelligence and decisions are reflected in the final product.

3.2 Flywheel Materials Numeric Data Base

An entirely different class of data bases is represented by the numeric data base. Lists of materials pertinent to the subject, in this case flywheels, are evaluated through processes described in Section 2.1. A spectrum of material properties is then compiled; properties included are mechanical, chemical, thermodynamic, electromagnetic, nuclear, etc. These properties are then evaluated by NBS-affiliated data evaluation centers (see Section 2.2). The evaluated property data are subsequently computerized at LLL.

Two flywheel-related data requests have been made. The first consists of a list of twenty-two metals and alloys, together with nine properties for each material. The second data request contains sixteen fiber materials (sixteen properties each), thirteen epoxy resins (twenty-seven properties each), and six polyester resins (twenty-seven properties each). Evaluation of the flywheel metals data request is close to completion. The evaluations for the fibers and matrix materials data request are still in progress. (See the Appendix for detailed lists of materials and properties and a sample fiber composite data sheet.)

We are placing particular emphasis on making numeric data bases interactive. Our goal is to allow the uninitiated user to sit down at a terminal and be able to not only retrieve specific data, but to do on-line manipulations of the data as well. Another goal is to allow the user to do on-line calculations with functional equations, since many of the properties are reported in functional form, i.e., as empirical equations with sets of coefficients which fit the data within specific bounds of temperature, pressure, etc. Finally, we intend to make the data bases interactive so that the user, by a simple keyboard command, can print or otherwise display entire tables of data.

Computer graphics is also being pursued actively. Often a graphical representation, such as a phase diagram, is the only form of information available for a property or relationship. Digitizing such graphical material and reconstructing it on television monitors or x-y plotters, is a current project.

Other minor sophistications such as conversions between systems of units of measurement are being built into the computer system to provide additional convenience to the user.

In general, an interactive numeric data base, such as the one proposed for flywheels, can be a powerful research tool, potentially very versatile, easily maintained, and updated.

We welcome your comments and suggestions.

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Appendix

Tables of Flywheel-Related Materials and Properties
Submitted to NBS for Evaluation

Table I. Priorities for fibers in flywheel rotors.

Fibers	Priority ^a
Kevlar 49	1
Kevlar 29	1
S-glass, 901	1
S-glass, 903	1
S2-glass	1
E-glass, Type 30, 410	1
E-glass, Type 30, 475	1
E-glass, multiend rovings	1
Carbon fiber	2
Magnamite AS1 (Hercules, Inc.)	
Magnamite AS2 (Hercules, Inc.)	
Morganite, Type 1 (Morganite Modmor, Inc.)	
Morganite, Type 2 (Morganite Modmor, Inc.)	
Morganite, Type 3 (Morganite Modmor, Inc.)	
Panex 30 C (Stackpole Fibers Co.)	
Graphite fiber	2
Thornel 300 (Union Carbide)	
Thornel 50 (Union Carbide)	
Thornel 75 (Union Carbide)	
Magnamite HTS (Hercules, Inc.)	
Fortafil CG5 (Great Lakes Carbon Corp.)	
Celion 2000 (Celanese Research Corp.)	
GSCY 2.10 (Carborundum Co.)	
Quartz fiber	2
Dacron, Hi Tenacity (Polyester)	3
Nylon 6, Hi Tenacity	3
Nylon 6,6, Hi Tenacity	3
Rayon, Hi Tenacity (Fortisan - 36)	3
Amorphous glass-like metal alloys	3
METGLASS Alloy 2826 (Allied Chemical)	
METGLASS Alloy 2605 (Allied Chemical)	
METGLASS Alloy 2605A (Allied Chemical)	
METGLASS Alloy 2204 (Allied Chemical)	

^aThe priorities refer to the fact that (1) a particular fiber will probably be used in a system; (2) it might be used; and (3) it probably won't be used.

Table II. Priorities for properties of fibers in flywheel rotors.

Property	Priority
Density	1
Elastic modulus	1
Tensile stress	1
Strain at ultimate stress	1
Usable (design) tensile strength	1
Upper use temperature	1
Creep	1
Elongation	1
Surface treatment	2
Filament diameter	2
Filaments per tow	2
Moisture absorbency	2
Thermal expansion coefficient	3
Poisson's ratio	3
Thermal conductivity	3
Specific heat	3
Electrical and magnetic properties of the amorphous, glass-like, metal alloys	3

Table III. Priorities for matrix systems in fiber composite flywheels.

Epoxy resin systems	Priority
XD 7818/XD 7575.02/ERL 4206/Tonox 60-40	1
DER 332/T-403	1
XD 7818/XD 7114/Tonox 60-40/DAP	1
Epon 826/RD-2/Tonox 60-40	1
XD 7818/T-403	1
XD 7818/XD 7114/Epon 871/Tonox 60-40, a & b	1
XD 7818/XD 7575.02/XD 7114/Tonox 60-40/DAP	2
XD 7818/XD 7575.02/ERL 4206/Tonox 60-40/DAP	2
XD 7818/XD 7114/Epirez 505/Tonox 60-40, a & b	2
XD 7818/DER 732/Tonox 60-40, a & b	2
XD 7818/XD 7114/ATBN/Tonox 60-40	2
ERE 1359/RD-2/DAP	2
<u>Polyester resins</u>	
DeraKane 411C	1
Epocryl 480	1
Atlac 382	1
Koppers 1010-5	2
Koppers 1201-5	2
Koppers 6030-5	2

Table IV. Properties of cured resins.

	Priority
Composition (types and amount)	1
Resins	
Diluent	
Curing agents	
Cure schedule	1
Tensile properties	1
Maximum stress	
Stress at failure	
Strain at maximum stress	
Strain at failure	
Elastic modulus in tension	
Compressive properties	1
Maximum compressive strength	
Strain at maximum strength	
Secant modulus	
Shear properties	1
Stress at failure	
Shear modulus	
Viscosity at 25°C	1
Time for viscosity to reach 2.0 Pa·s	1
Gel time	1
Exotherm of 500 g from 25°C	2
Density (uncured) at 25°C	1
Density (cured) at 25°C	1
Shrinkage (% volume)	1
After gelation	
After cure	
Water absorption	1
Glass transition temperature	1
Heat distortion temperature	1
Specific heat	2
Heat capacity	2
Thermal coefficient of linear expansion	2
Thermal conductivity	2

Table V. Sample of a fiber composite data sheet.

<u>Fiber Properties</u>		<u>Number of Sources</u>
<u>E-HTS Fiberglass Roving</u>		
Tensile strength		
Individual virgin fiber strength	500,000 psi (3445 MPa)	
Std. dev.	60,000 psi (413 MPa)	
Modulus	10-11 x 10 ⁶ psi (68.9 - 75.8 GPa)	
Elongation	4.8%	
Diameter	0.000035 - 0.000040 inch (0.000089 - 0.00010 cm)	
Roving strength (resin impregnated)		
Best value*	300,000 psi (2067 MPa)	9
<u>Resin Properties</u>		
<u>Epon 828/Metaphenylenediamine 100/14.5</u>		
Volume shrinkage, %	5.9	3
Density cured resin, g/cc	1.21	
Water absorption, 28 days @ 23°C, %	0.91	
Heat distortion temperature	150° ± 5°C	3
Tensile strength - break	86.8 MPa ± 1.65 MPa	4
Elongation - break, %	5.2 ± 0.7	4
Modulus	3.31 GPa	4
Compressive stress yield	10,500 psi (72 MPa)	3
Modulus	310,000 psi (2.1 GPa)	3
<u>Composite Properties</u>		
<u>E-HTS Fiberglass and Epon 828</u>		
Tensile	200,000 psi ± 8300 psi (1370 MPa ± 57 MPa)	5
Elongation	2.6 ± 0.5%	
* Values of 398,000 ± 12,000 psi (2742 MPa ± 82.7 MPa) (2760 samples) have been obtained under optimum fabrication procedures on strand tests and values of 351,000 ± 16,000 psi (2418 MPa ± 110 MPa) on cylinders tested hydrostatically		2
		2

Table VI. Priorities for metals and metal alloys in flywheel rotors.

	Priority
Aluminum 6061-T6	1
Aluminum 7075-T6	1
Stainless steel, 15-7Mo	1
Steel 4340	1
Maraging steel 18 Ni-300	1
Titanium 6Al-4V	1
Aluminum 2024-T851	2
Stainless steel cast AM 355	2
Stainless steel custom 455	2
Stainless steel 440C	2
Steel 1020	2
Steel 1040	2
Steel H-11	2
Cobalt MP 35N	3
Stainless steel 216	3
Steel C1141	3
Maraging steel 18 Ni-400	3
Steel, Unitemp 212	3
Steel, V-57	3
Titanium, 6Al-4V-2.5Sn	3
Titanium, 8Mo-8V-2Fe-3Al	3
Titanium, 2Mo-0.25Si	3

Table VII. Priorities for properties of metals and metal alloys in flywheel rotors

	Priority
Young's modulus	1
Shear modulus	1
Bulk modulus	1
Poisson's ratio	1
Yield strength	1
Ultimate strength	1
Creep strength	1
Fatigue strength	1

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